

**DASTURIY TA'LIM VOSITALARI ASOSIDA TALABALARNI TEXNIK-
KOSTRUKTORLIK KOMPENENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH**

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Annotatsiya: Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalarning texnik ijodkorlik va konstruksiyalash hamda kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish tushunchasi, psixologik va pedagogik mohiyati tizimli tahlil qilindi, servis xizmati yo'nalishi talabalarining ijtimoiy-pedagogik xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqib, tikuvchilikka oid kompetensiyalari, konstruksion usullari, vositalari, parametrlarini aniqlash bo'yicha, talabalarning texnik ijodkorlik qobiliyatlari rivojlanatirildi va tikuvchilik buyumlarini konstruksiyalash va modellashtirish bosqichlari o'rganildi, talabalarning servis xizmati yo'nalishida texnik ijodkorlik va grafik-hisoblash ko'nikmalari, konstruksiyalash, modellashtirish usullar, kompyuter dasturlaridan foydalanish afzalliklari va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ushbu maqolada asoslab berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Power point dasturi, dasturiy ta'lim, ijodkorlik, grafik-hisoblash, modellashtirish usullar.

Аннотация: В высших учебных заведениях систематически анализировались понятия технического творчества и строительства, а также формирования профессиональных компетенций, психологического и редакционного значения студентов, исходя из социально-педагогических особенностей студентов сервисного факультета, определялись навыки шитья, способы конструирования, инструменты, параметры, развивались навыки технического творчества учащихся и изучались этапы конструирования и моделирования швейных изделий, навыки технического творчества и графо-расчета учащихся в сфере обслуживания, строительства. В статье изучены методы моделирования, преимущества и особенности использования компьютерных программ.

Ключевые слова: программа Power Point, обучение программному обеспечению, творчество, графический расчет, методы моделирования.

Annotation: The concept, psychological and editorial meaning of the formation of technical creativity and construction and professional competencies of students in higher education institutions was systematically analyzed, based on the socio-pedagogical characteristics of service students, the sewing skills, construction methods, tools, parameters were determined. on, students' technical creativity skills were developed and the stages of construction and modeling of sewing products were studied, students' technical creativity and graphic-calculation skills in the direction of service, construction, modeling methods, advantages and unique features of using computer programs features were explained in this article.

Key words: Power point program, software education, creativity, graphic calculation, modeling methods.

Jahonda globallashuv hamda ta'limning integratsiyalashuvi jarayonlari chuqurlashayotgan hozirgi davrda "Texnologik ta'lim" yo'nalishi talabalarining texnik-konstruktorlik kompetentligini rivojlantirishda 3D modellashtirish, texnologik jarayonlarni loyihalashga ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda. Dunyoda ilmning chegarasi yo'qdir. Ilm-fan, xususan ilmiy faoliyat hozirgi kunda dunyodagi istalgan mamlakat rivoji uchun o'ta muhimdir. Chunki ijtimoiy hayotning ko'pgina sohalarini o'z rivojida ilm-fan yutuqlari, ilmiy ishlanmalardan keng foydalanib kelmoqda.

Hozirgi vaqtda Angliya, Fransiya, Yaponiya, Germaniya, Janubiy Koreya, Rossiya, Hindiston, Kanada kabi rivojlangan davlatlari ta'lim jarayonida yuqori kasbiy faoliyatga ega, raqobatbardosh kadrlar tayyorlash, talabalarning texnik-konstruktorlik kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish, shu jumladan, o'qitish jarayoniga kompyuter dasturlarini tadbiq etishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Aytish joizki, mamlakatimizda ilm-fanga intilish va virtual ta'lim muhitini shakllantirish, yoshlarni ilmiy faoliyatga jalb etish maqsadida, oliy ta'lim tizimida PhotoSHOP, CorelDRAW, Macromedia Flash, 3ds MAX hamda AutoCAD dasturida turli formatlar, kompyuter dizayni,

raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda turli dasturlardan foydalanib, elektron darsliklar, virtual laboratoriyalar hamda mobil ilovalar yaratilmoqda.

Bugungi kunda mustaqil hayotga kirib kelayotgan har bir yosh avlodga ilmiy-texnik, texnologik-konstruktiv, loyixalash, modellashtirish, iqtisodiyot va ishlab chiqarish asoslariga oid zamonaviy kompyuter dasturlaridan foydalanishga oid bilimlarni berish, intellektual salohiyatlarini yanada rivojlantirish, atrofdagi voqea va hodislarga ijodiy munosabatda bo'lishlari muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Talabalarning texnik-konstruktorlik kreativligini boshqarish tasavvuri bilan shug'ullanish jarayonida ixtirochilik va tadqiqotchilik, konstruktiv-modellashtirish faoliyatlariga motivatsiyalarini rivojlantirish bugungi kunda dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Talabalarning texnik ijodkorlik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish masalalariga qaratilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Dunyodagi innovatsiyalarni ta'lim jarayoniga tadbqiq etish, talabalarning tikuvchilik buyumlarini konstruksiyalash va modellashtirishga oid kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish usullarini ilmiy asoslab berish, ta'lim tizimi mazmuniga mos innovasion o'qitish metodikasini joriy etish va o'quv materiallarini takomillashtirish zaruriyati yuzaga kelmoqda.

Texnik ijodkorlik va konstruksiyalash fanini o'qitishda AutoCAD dasturlaridan foydalanib, talabalarning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlarini inobatga olib, ijtimoiylik, intellektuallik, axborot, texnologik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan loyiha texnologiyasini qo'llab o'qitish metodikasini ishlab chiqiq.

Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida "Texnik ijodkorlik va konstruksiyalash" fanini o'qitishda loyiha texnologiyasi qo'llanilganda ta'lim sifati oshganligi, shuningdek talabalarning ijodiy qobiliyatlari ancha rivojlanganligi kuzatildi.

Power point dasturi asosida ayollar ko'ylagini konstruksiyalash va modellashtirishning texnologik xaritasi

2.4-jadval

№	Ish ketma-ketligi.	Ish eskizi	Standart asosida operatsiyani bajarish tartibi
1.	Power Point dasturidan yangi oyna ochib, orqa fon tanlaymiz		
2	Power Point dasturiga ishchi panelli.	<p>Ko'ylakning asosiy chizmasi uchun quyidagi o'lchovlar kerak (sm hisobida)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bo'yin aylanasi – 18 sm Ko'krak aylanasi – 48 sm Oldingi yeng o'zining uzunligi – 30,5 sm Orqa yeng o'zining uzunligi – 19 sm Orqa kakatkaning kengligi – 17 sm Kaketka oldining kengligi – 15 sm Ko'ylakning umumiy uzunligi – 115 sm Yeng uzunligi – 60 sm 	Power Point dasturida ishchi panelli oynasida ayollar ko'ylagi uchun olingan o'lchovlar kiritiladi.
3	Power Point dasturiga ishchi panelli.	<p>ASOS CHIZMASI</p>	Power Point dasturida ishchi panelli oynasida ayollar ko'ylagi uchun olingan o'lchovlar kiritilgandan so'ng, yangi oyna ochib katak fon hosil qilib, shakllar tanlab olinadi.

4	Power dasturiga paneli.	Point ishchi		Yuqoridagi o'lchamlar asosida ayollar ko'ylagini old bo'lakgi kerakli shakllar orqali chiziladi
5	Power dasturiga	Point		
6	Power dasturiga	Point		
7	Power dasturiga	Point		
8	Power dasturiga	Point		
9	Power dasturiga	Point		
10	Power dasturiga	Point		

11	Power dasturiga Point		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AH=135 SM AG=135 SM AC=135 SM GG=545 SM AA=545 SM AR=6 SM RR=235 SM PP=1 SM CC=3 SM CC=6 SM CC=3 SM VV=1 SM AA=3 SM BB=3 SM
12	Power dasturiga Model chiziqlar o'lchamda ko'riladi Point		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AH=135 SM AG=135 SM AC=135 SM GG=545 SM AA=545 SM AR=6 SM RR=235 SM PP=1 SM CC=3 SM CC=6 SM CC=3 SM VV=1 SM AA=3 SM BB=3 SM VV=2 SM VV=4 SM

Texnik ijodkorlik va konstruksiyalash fanini o'qitishda Power Point dasturlaridan foydalanib, loyiha texnologiyasini qo'llab o'qitish metodikasini ishlab chiqilgan. Bu esa talabalarni rivojlantirishda ko'proq yangi ilmiy g'oyalarning tadqiqotchisi va amalga oshiruvchisi bo'lib xizmat qiladi hamda unda hayotga, mehnatga, o'z kasbiga nisbatan innovasion yondashuvi shakllandi. Demak, ta'lim jarayonida kompyuter texnologiyalarni kiritish orqali talabalarning texnik ijodkorlik qobiliyati rivojlanadi hamda baholash va o'zlashtirish jarayoni masalalarini ijobiy hal qilishda innovasion muhim yordam beradi.

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